

Observation of *Euchromius superbellus* (Zeller, 1849) in Hungary (Lepidoptera, Crambidae)

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Abstract. In 2025, the first documented occurrence of *Euchromius superbellus* in Hungary is reported, based on an authenticated photographic record. Before this observation, neither published records nor collection data had confirmed the presence of the species within the country's borders. The specimen was observed during evening hours on a white collecting sheet illuminated by artificial light in a private garden located in the suburban zone of Dunaújváros, a central Hungarian industrial city. The surrounding area is characterised by intensive transport infrastructure, including major motorways and shipping routes along the Danube River, as well as nearby port facilities. The occurrence is presumed to be accidental, potentially resulting from passive transport via commercial shipments or dispersal facilitated by strong winds originating from the Adriatic region. The species' status in Hungary remains uncertain and requires verification through targeted faunistic surveys and long-term monitoring.

Keywords. new data, faunistics, bionomics, geographical distribution

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Introduction

Until recently, only two species of the genus *Euchromius* Guenée, 1845 have been recorded from Hungary: *E. ocella* (Haworth, [1811]) and *E. bella* (Hübner, 1796) (Fazekas, 2011; Buschmann & Pastoralis, 2025). Szent-Ivány and Uhrík-Mészáros (1942: 129) reported two specimens of *E. superbellus* bearing the label “Hung. ANKER. coll. REBEL.” These specimens most likely originated from the Adriatic coastal region during the period of the former Austro-Hungarian Monarchy. From a historical perspective, no subsequent observations have confirmed the presence of *E. superbellus* within the post-Trianon borders of Hungary up to 2021. This conclusion was also supported by Gozmány (1963) and Fazekas (2011). Furthermore, Slamka (2008) indicated Hungary with a question mark on the distribution map, reflecting uncertainty regarding the species' occurrence.

On 18 August 2025, Sándor Farkas photographed a specimen of *E. superbellus*. He used a 12-volt UV LED strip for primary lighting, supplemented by smaller UV lights and a 5-volt white light reflector in the garden of his family home in Dunaújváros, central Hungary. Based on the wing pattern, the specimen was highly likely to represent *E. superbellus*, a species previously unrecorded from Hungary. Following consultation with several colleagues (including C. Plant, S. Gomboc, G. Baldizzone, G. Bassi and R. Schuten), a consensus was reached confirming that the photographed individual was indeed *E. superbellus*. According to Gomboc (pers. comm.), the occurrence may be associated with transport routes: “Is the locality connected with transport, such as a railway station where containers are handled, for example, from the port of Koper or the port of Rijeka? Or is it close to an industrial zone where such containers are delivered? The specimen could also have arrived by other means of transport, such as ships, which are illuminated and may attract moths that can remain on deck for several days.”

Recent trends in European lepidopterological research indicate a methodological transition in the criteria used to validate faunistic records. Historically, only physically collected, pre-

pared, and curated specimens were regarded as definitive evidence for confirming a species' presence within a given region. This traditional approach ensured long-term verifiability, facilitated repeated morphological examination, and supported future taxonomic revisions. In contrast, contemporary researchers increasingly consider high-quality, metadata-supported photographic documentation to be sufficient for establishing species occurrences. Advances in digital imaging and georeferencing technologies now allow photographs to provide reliable, expert, verifiable evidence, particularly for taxa that are morphologically distinctive and do not require microscopic or genetic analysis for accurate identification. This shift also reduces the need for specimen collection, which is especially advantageous for rare or protected species. While physical specimens remain indispensable for taxonomically complex groups, cryptic species, and formal species descriptions, the broader acceptance of photographic evidence represents a pragmatic and ethically informed evolution in faunistic methodology.

The present study aims to document the first confirmed occurrence of *E. superbellus* in Hungary and to evaluate whether its appearance represents natural dispersal, accidental introduction, or human-mediated transport.

Material and methods

The maps, line drawings, and figures were prepared by the first author using CorelDRAW 2025. The study is based on photographic documentation obtained on 22 June 2025 in Dunaújváros under artificial lighting conditions. Species identification relied on the examination of diagnostic morphological characters of the wing pattern and was corroborated through consultation with international experts. In addition, a comparative morphological analysis was conducted, with particular emphasis on distinguishing the species from *Euchromius rayatella*. Relevant literature concerning the species' distribution and ecology was also critically reviewed. From a methodological perspective, the present study reflects contemporary faunistic practice, which increasingly recognises the validity of well-documented photographic records as reliable evidence. The text is the work of the first author.

Euchromius superbellus (Zeller, 1849)

Crambus superbellus Zeller, 1849, Ent. Ztg. Stett. 10: 314. Locus typicus Italien, Toscana. Holotype ♂ in coll. British Museum, London.

Syn.: *Euromius wockeella* Zeller, 1863; *Ommatoptreux syriusella* Amsel, 1858.

New data from Hungary. Dunaújváros (46.972556, 18.913546) on 18 August 2025 | 00:28 | photo: S. Farkas | With PENTAX 50 mm MACRO lens and SUNPAK PT-2D ring flash.

External diagnostic characters (habitus). The two species are externally very similar and often difficult to separate based solely on wing pattern; however, the following characters may assist in tentative identification. The forewing pattern of *Euchromius superbellus* is generally more contrasting, with longitudinal pale streaks appearing sharper and more distinctly defined. In contrast, *Euchromius rayatella* exhibits a more diffuse pattern, with longitudinal streaks less clearly delineated. Ground colour also differs subtly between the two taxa. In *E. superbellus*, the forewing ground colour is typically lighter, often with a more pronounced golden or yellowish hue. In *E. rayatella*, the overall colouration tends to be duller, dominated by greyish-brown tones. The discal spot on the forewing provides an additional, though variable, character. In *E. superbellus*, the discal spot is usually indistinct or may be absent, whereas in *E. rayatella* it is more frequently present and appears as a distinct dark mark.

These external characters should be used with caution, as intraspecific variation may overlap; reliable identification generally requires examination of the genitalia.

Genital diagnostic characters. Reliable separation of *Euchromius superbellus* and *E. rayatella* requires examination of the genitalia in both sexes; the following characters are considered the most important differential features.

Male genitalia. In *Euchromius superbellus*, the valva is distinctly narrower and more elongate, with a comparatively slender appearance. The cucullus is more tapering and apically acute, often appearing slightly produced. The costa is less expanded, and the overall valval

Fig. 1. Diagnostic characters of the wing patterns of *Euchromius superbellus* (a) and *E. rayatella* (b)

Fig. 2. *Euchromius superbellus*, Hungary: Dunaújváros (46.972556, 18.913546) on 18 August 2025 | Photo: S. Farkas. Black dot: Dunaújváros, the dotted black lines indicate the presumed immigration route.

Figs 3-4. Diagnostic characters (indicated) of male and female genitalia: **3.** *Euchromius superbellus*; **4.** *E. rayatella* (From Fazekas 2017)

outline is more parallel-sided. The sacculus is relatively weakly developed. In *Euchromius rayatella*, the valva is broader and more robust, with a more rounded general outline. The cucullus is apically blunt and less produced. The costa tends to be more expanded, contributing to a stouter appearance of the valva. The sacculus is typically more pronounced.

Female genitalia. In *Euchromius superbellus*, the ductus bursae is generally longer and more slender, often with a more uniform width. The corpus bursae tends to be more elongate, and the signum is comparatively smaller and less heavily sclerotised. In *Euchromius rayatella*, the ductus bursae is shorter and relatively broader. The corpus bursae is more rounded, and the signum is usually larger and more strongly sclerotised, often appearing more conspicuous.

Distribution and Habitat. *Euchromius superbellus* is distributed across southern and eastern Europe, as well as western Asia, with confirmed records from France, Spain, Italy, Croatia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Romania, Bulgaria, North Macedonia, Albania, Greece, Russia, Transcaucasia, Turkey, and Armenia. Its occurrence in Central Europe (e.g., Austria, Hungary, Slovenia) has been regarded as uncertain or problematic in several regional faunistic accounts.

Fig. 5. The hypothetical distribution range of the two closely related species in the Western Palearctic: red line: *Euchromius superbellus*, black dotted line: *E. rayatella*. The center of distribution for both species is in the Euro-Mediterranean biogeographical region. The boundaries of the eastern and northern fluctuation areas are constantly changing.

The new Hungarian observation site and its wider area can be described as a non-native deciduous forest and plantations mixed with native trees, uncharacteristic dry grasslands, scattered native or narrow tree lines, dry and semi-dry pioneer scrub, Scots and black pine plantations and spontaneous stands of non-native trees.

According to Stanisław Błeszyński (1965), the range of *E. superbellus* overlaps with that of *Euchromius rayatella* in Italy and the Balkan Peninsula, as well as with *Euchromius gozmani* in Spain.

The first author investigated characteristic habitats along the Dalmatian coast (Neum) and in Italy (Levanto), documenting these environments in two figures (Figs 6–7). Comparable sub-Mediterranean habitats occur in Central Europe, primarily in southern Hungary (e.g., the Villány Mountains [Fig 8.]) and, more sporadically, further north in the Bakony Mountains. These ecological analogues suggest that colonisation of the region by *E. superbellus* is plausible; however, this hypothesis requires confirmation through targeted faunistic surveys.

Phenology and Ecology. Field collection data indicate adult flight activity in June and September, typically at elevations ranging from about 700 to 1750 m in some regions of its range.

Ecology and distribution of *Euchromius superbellus* (Lepidoptera: Crambidae) in Europe, with comparative notes on *Euchromius rayatella*. Available evidence suggests that *Euchromius superbellus* is associated with warm, xerothermic habitats in southern and sub-Mediterranean Europe. Most records originate from open, sun-exposed environments, including dry grasslands and steppe-like habitats, indicating a preference for thermally favourable conditions (Slamka, 2008). Although direct ecological data are lacking, its habitat association appears consistent with other members of Crambinae, whose larvae typically develop on Poaceae (Landry 1995). Records from the Mediterranean and Balkan regions further support its occurrence in dry, open landscapes, often with sparse vegetation (e.g. Bassi et al., 2013; Vives Moreno 2014).

Figs 6–7. The preferred habitats of *Euchromius superbellus* are in the Mediterranean; 6. Neum area in Juli 1996 (Bosnia and Herzegovina) 7. Levanto in August 2014 (Italy). Photos: © I. Fazekas

Fig 8. The potential habitat of *Euchromius superbellus* is in southern Hungary, in the Villány Mountains. The rocky grasslands are home to numerous Mediterranean plant and insect species. Photo: © I. Fazekas

The available distribution data indicate that *E. superbellus* has a predominantly southern range, with only occasional and scattered records north of the Mediterranean zone. This pattern suggests limited dispersal capacity and a primarily resident population structure. At present, there is no direct evidence supporting regular migratory behaviour in this species.

In contrast, *Euchromius rayatella* exhibits a wider distribution encompassing southern Europe, North Africa, and large parts of Asia, and is repeatedly recorded outside its core range. Its presence in Central Europe is best explained by recurrent immigration events, consistent with a migratory life strategy (Slamka 2008; Bassi et al. 2013).

Ecologically, *E. rayatella* appears less restricted, occurring in a broader spectrum of habitats, including dry grasslands, coastal dunes, and various disturbed environments. This pattern is well documented in Mediterranean and Balkan faunistic surveys, where the species is frequently associated with ruderal and anthropogenic habitats (Bassi et al., 2013; Vives Moreno 2014). Such ecological plasticity likely facilitates its dispersal and temporary establishment outside its primary range.

Overall, the available data suggest that *Euchromius superbellus* represents a more regionally constrained and possibly less mobile species, whereas *Euchromius rayatella* is characterized by broader ecological tolerance and recurrent dispersal. However, these conclusions remain tentative due to the limited availability of species-specific ecological data, particularly for *E. superbellus*. Targeted faunistic and ecological studies, especially in transitional zones of Central and southeastern Europe, are needed to clarify the extent of its distribution and dispersal dynamics.

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(Magyar nyelvű összefoglaló)

Az *Euchromius superbellus* (Zeller, 1849) megfigyelése Magyarországon (Lepidoptera, Crambidae)

Fazekas Imre & Farkas Sándor

A tanulmány a *Euchromius superbellus* első hiteles magyarországi előfordulását vizsgálja, valamint értékeli annak biogeográfiai és faunisztikai jelentőségét.

Kutatási kérdés. A vizsgálat központi kérdése annak meghatározása, hogy a *Euchromius superbellus* magyarországi megjelenése egy stabilan megtelepedett populáció jelenlétére utal-e, vagy inkább alkalmi, véletlenszerű előfordulásról (pl. behurcolás vagy természetes diszperzió) van szó.

Módszer. A kutatás alapját egy 2025. augusztus 18-án, Dunaújvárosban készült fotódokumentáció képezte, amelyet mesterséges fényforrás alkalmazásával gyűjtöttek. A faji azonosítás a szárnymintázat morfológiai bélyegei alapján, valamint nemzetközi szakértőkkel való konzultáció révén történt. A szerzők összehasonlító morfológiai elemzést is végeztek, különös tekintettel a *Euchromius rayatella*-val való elkülönítésre, továbbá áttekintették a faj elterjedésére és ökológiájára vonatkozó szakirodalmat. A tanulmány módszertani szempontból reflektál a modern faunisztikai gyakorlatra is, amely egyre inkább elfogadja a hiteles fényképes bizonyítékokat.

Eredmények. A vizsgálat megerősítette a *Euchromius superbellus* első bizonyított előfordulását Magyarországon. Az eredmények alapján a faj jelenléte valószínűleg nem egy állandó populációhoz köthető, hanem inkább véletlenszerű behurcolás vagy légköri diszperzió következménye. A lelőhely környezeti adottságai (intenzív közlekedési és ipari infrastruktúra) alátámasztják ezt az értelmezést. A faj ökológiai igényei alapján ugyanakkor elméletileg lehetséges lenne a megtelepedés szubmediterrán jellegű élőhelyeken Magyarország déli és középső területein. Az összehasonlító elemzés rámutatott, hogy a *E. superbellus* elkülönítése a morfológiailag hasonló fajoktól sok esetben csak genitália-vizsgálattal lehetséges, ami hangsúlyozza a klasszikus taxonómiai módszerek jelentőségét.

Következtetések. A tanulmány jelentős új faunisztikai adatot szolgáltat, ugyanakkor rámutat arra, hogy a faj hazai státusza jelenleg bizonytalan. A szerzők további célzott vizsgálatokat és hosszú távú monitorozást javasolnak annak tisztázására, hogy a faj képes-e tartósan megtelepedni Magyarországon a potencilás habitatokban, főleg a Dunántúlon (Bakony, Mecsek, Villányi-hegység).

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Note: In our work, we mainly analysed and used data from the following publications.

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